

DISAC

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Final version of scenarios, use cases and KPIs

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Abstract

The rapid evolution of wireless communication technologies has driven the transition from 4G to 5G, unlocking capabilities such as mobile broadband, low latency, and scalable communications. Now, the advent of 6G represents a fundamental shift, redefining the role of radio signals to seamlessly integrate both communications and sensing functionalities. Integrated Sensing and Communications (ISAC) has become a key area of research for 6G networks; however, despite substantial progress, ISAC systems often remain at low Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs), highlighting the need for further development.

This deliverable addresses the challenges that the concept of Distributed and Intelligent Integrated Sensing and Communications (DISAC) must overcome. DISAC emphasises widespread, collaborative deployments involving multiple sensing and communication nodes rather than isolated single-node setups. In addition to traditional Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), this work incorporates Key Value Indicators (KVI) and introduces new metrics such as sensing data volume, power consumption, and processing cost, all of which critically impact system architecture and design. Special attention is given to analysing trade-offs between radio resource allocation for sensing versus communication, as well as balancing processing demands, power costs, and sensing accuracy.

This document outlines the 6G-DISAC project's scenarios, use cases, and KPI framework, focusing on how DISAC can enhance ISAC applications. It reviews use cases identified by major Standards Development Organisations (SDOs), applies the DISAC framework to improve selected ISAC cases, and explores technical solutions for the joint optimisation of sensing and communication. Through this deliverable, a roadmap is provided for the implementation and advancement of ISAC use cases with the DISAC approach, setting a foundation for future innovations in the 6G landscape.

Keywords

6G; Integrated Sensing and Communications (ISAC); Distributed ISAC (DISAC); Key Performance Indicators (KPIs); Key Value Indicators (KVI); Smart Factory; Vulnerable Road User (VRU) Protection; Semantic Communications; Wireless Communication Technologies.

Disclaimer

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

ADAS	Advanced Driver Assistance Systems
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AP	Access Point
AWGN	Additive White Gaussian Noise
BCE	Binary Cross Entropy
BS	Base Station
CAPEX	Capital Expenditures
CFR	Channel Frequency Response
CIR	Channel Impulse Response
CRB	Cramér-Rao Bound
CSePF	Centralised Sensing Processing Function
D-MIMO	Distributed Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
DISAC	Distributed and Intelligent Integrated Sensing and Communication
DL	Downlink
EMF	Electromagnetic field
FDD	Frequency Division Duplexing
FLOPS	Floating Point Operations per Second
FR	Frequency Range
ISAC	Integrated Sensing and Communications
ISG ISAC	Industry Specification Group for ISAC
JCAS	Joint Communication and Sensing
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KVI	Key Value Indicator
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LSePF	Local Sensing Processing Function
MIMO	Multiple Input Multiple Output
ML	Machine Learning
MLW	Main Lobe Width
mmWave	Millimeter Wave
MSE	Mean Squared Error
NTN	Non-Terrestrial Network
OPEX	Operational Expenditures:
PEB	Position Error Bound
PHY	PHYsical layer
PoC	Proof of Concept
PRU	Positioning Reference Unit
PSL	Peak Sidelobe Level
QoS	Quality of Service
RIS	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
SAE	Society of Automobile Engineers
SCFD	Sensing Communications Frequency Division
SCSD	Sensing Communications Space Division

SCTD	Sensing Communications Time Division
SDO	Standard Development Organisation
SeMF	Sensing Management Function
SER	Symbol Error Rate
SINR	Signal to Interferences and Noise Ratio
SLAM	Simultaneous Localisation and Mapping
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
SotA	State of the Art
SSE	Semantic Spectral Efficiency
TDD	Time Division Duplexing
TDoA	Time Difference of Arrival
TIG	Technical Interest Group
TR	Technical Report
UE	User Equipment
UL	Uplink
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WG	Work Group
WP	Work Package
XRXR	Extended Reality

1 Introduction

Recent advancements in the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) have marked a pivotal shift in the integration of sensing capabilities into wireless networks, particularly in the transition toward 6G. Unlike previous generations, where sensing was peripheral, recent 3GPP releases, particularly under the scope of Release 18 and beyond 3GPP WS Rel 18/19, have formally acknowledged sensing as a key feature, paving the way for native support of Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC). This shift reflects a broader evolution from 4G and 5G, which prioritised mobile broadband and low latency, toward 6G's transformative vision of radio signals not only as communication tools but also as active sensors enabling situational awareness, intelligence, and network reconfigurability for sensing.

ISAC is no longer viewed simply as an extension of communication technologies, but rather as a foundational pillar of 6G, enabling systems to perceive and interact with their environments in real time [URB+21]. However, while the conceptual framework for ISAC is maturing, the technology remains at relatively low readiness levels, particularly for large-scale and real-world deployment. A major limitation in current ISAC designs is their narrow focus on traditional Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), such as throughput and latency, without adequately incorporating Key Value Indicators (KVIs), which reflect the broader societal, environmental, and operational impacts of network functionalities.

The importance of integrating KVIs alongside KPIs becomes especially pronounced in the context of distributed sensing. In fact, future ISAC systems must support wide-area deployments capable of tracking vast numbers of connected user equipments (UEs) and passive objects across both time and space. This requires a paradigm shift—not just in signal design, but in how network intelligence is measured and valued. Metrics like energy efficiency, context awareness, adaptability, and contribution to safety (KVIs) will be just as crucial as conventional KPIs in determining the success of distributed ISAC solutions.

To meet these evolving demands, the Distributed and Intelligent Integrated Sensing and Communication (DISAC) framework has been introduced. DISAC emphasises the fusion of heterogeneous, distributed sensors and adopts a semantic-native, adaptive architecture designed for high-resolution, energy-efficient environmental sensing. It addresses the current ISAC shortcomings by enabling scalable, intelligent tracking solutions that bridge communication and perception across a wide array of 6G use cases.

This document, Deliverable D2.3, serves as the final and consolidated version of the scenario, use cases, and KPI analysis, building upon and extending the groundwork laid in Deliverable [6GDISAC-D21]. While [6GDISAC-D21] introduced the foundational DISAC use cases and their relevance to 6G ISAC evolution, D2.3 focuses on how these use cases will be realistically deployed and scaled within the DISAC framework. A key emphasis is placed on how both KPIs and KVIs shape the direction and priorities of ISAC deployment. This broader perspective ensures that performance is not only measured in technical terms (e.g., latency, resolution, energy efficiency) but also in terms of real-world impact, such as safety, sustainability, and societal benefit.

Moreover, the specific KPI and KVI definitions for DISAC have been refined and aligned with the semantic-native, distributed nature of the framework, as detailed in deliverables [6GDISAC-D31] and [6GDISAC-D41]. Together, these deliverables provide a cohesive view of how DISAC will meet the complex demands of future 6G environments, where sensing and communication are deeply intertwined, and system success depends as much on value creation as on raw technical performance.

2 Overview of ISAC Use Cases in Various Standardisation Organisations

2.1 3GPP update in SA1

3GPP has extensively documented its work on sensing and positioning in previous deliverables, outlining various use cases that demonstrate the integration of these technologies into 5G and beyond. In particular, 3GPP Release 18 introduces ISAC, supporting applications such as autonomous driving, unmanned aerial vehicles, and industrial automation (3GPP TR 38.855).

The list of 32 use cases described by 3GPP in TR 22.837 has been detailed in the previous deliverable [6GDISAC-D21, Tab.1]. The 3GPP has not officially defined KVIs for sensing within its specifications. The concept of KVIs has emerged in the context of 6G discussions, particularly within European initiatives like the Hexa-X-II project, to assess broader societal and environmental impacts of future networks. 3GPP's current work continues to focus on defining and refining KPIs to assess and enhance sensing capabilities for the upcoming wireless networks.

The timeline for the sensing study has been updated in alignment with the overall timeline for the 6G study (WS-3GPP), as reflected in Figure 2-1. While sensing has not yet been confirmed for inclusion in the first phase (Day 1) of 6G, its development is structured to follow this updated timeline if it is agreed upon for early deployment. This ensures that the necessary technical studies and standardisation efforts progress in synchronisation with broader 6G advancements, allowing for a seamless integration of sensing capabilities should they be prioritised in the initial 6G release (see Figure 2-1).

Figure 2-1: 3GPP timeline for 6G and its impact on sensing.

2.2 IEEE update

In [6GDISAC-D21], it has been mentioned that IEEE is making significant strides in sensing technologies and AI/ML integration, particularly through its involvement in the 6G-DISAC project. A Technical Interest Group (TIG) has evolved into a permanent AI/ML Standing Committee, focusing on use cases like model distribution, channel access, and AI-based roaming to enhance Wi-Fi performance, improving efficiency, throughput, and user experience, with future extensions toward ISAC applications.

In parallel, IEEE is developing the **IEEE 802.11bf** standard, a major advancement in WLAN by embedding sensing capabilities into Wi-Fi [DHX+24]. This includes enhancements to PHY and MAC layers while maintaining backward compatibility. The standard supports applications like

presence detection, activity recognition, indoor localisation, and healthcare monitoring through non-invasive signal analysis. It introduces new sensing KPIs and technical innovations, such as waveform design and multi-device coordination, to enable collaborative, high-resolution sensing across multiple devices and frequency bands.

Beyond standardisation, IEEE is actively driving advancements in sensing technologies through a series of conferences and initiatives, covering a broad spectrum of research and development areas. These efforts span a wide range of sensing topics, including but not limited to:

1. **Sensor Networks:** Research on the development and deployment of sensor networks for various applications such as environmental monitoring, healthcare, and smart cities.
2. **IoT (Internet of Things):** Integration of sensors with IoT devices to collect and analyse data for improved decision-making.
3. **Wearable Sensors:** Development of sensors for wearable devices that monitor health metrics, physical activity, and other personal data.
4. **Environmental Sensing:** Sensors used for monitoring environmental parameters like air quality, water quality, and weather conditions.
5. **Automotive Sensing:** Sensors used in autonomous vehicles for navigation, obstacle detection, and safety features.
6. **Industrial Sensing:** Sensors used in industrial applications for monitoring machinery, processes, and safety.
7. **Biomedical Sensing:** Development of sensors for medical diagnostics, patient monitoring, and healthcare applications.
8. **Non-Terrestrial Network (NTN) Sensing:** Sensing capabilities integrated into Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN) like satellites and drones for remote sensing, environmental monitoring, and extending network functions beyond communication.

In this deliverable, we specifically highlight the expanded scope of sensing topics compared to the previous work, demonstrating how the breadth and diversity of IEEE’s initiatives have evolved to address emerging technological trends and interdisciplinary challenges.

2.3 ETSI update

ETSI launched an Industry Specification Group for ISAC (ISG ISAC) in November 2023. Work Group (WG) 1 deals with “ISAC Use Cases and Deployment Scenarios”. WG1 published a Group Report (GR) end of March 2025. It identifies 18 advanced use cases which go beyond those ones defined in 3GPP TR22.837 [[3GPP22.837](#)].

In this deliverable, in a manner compatible with 3GPP specifications, these new use cases are summarised in the table below reproduced from [ETSI GR ISAC001].

Table 2-1: ETSI use cases.

Use case	Deployment type	Sensing target type and mobility	Mapping to DISAC use cases
Human motion recognition	Indoor and/or outdoor	Human target, low mobility Fine movement detection	
Airborne-based sensing for environmental reconstruction	Outdoors	Low/Medium/high mobility	
Real-time monitoring of health hazard and disaster risk	Outdoors, mixed indoor-outdoor	All target types (human, vehicles, buildings, objects) with low/medium mobility	

Use case	Deployment type	Sensing target type and mobility	Mapping to DISAC use cases
Emergency search and rescue	Indoor and/or outdoor	Human target, static or low mobility (centimetre level)	
Remotely controlled robots for senior citizen monitoring and care	Indoor	Humans (static, low mobility) and objects	Use Case 1: DISAC for smart factory shop floors
Precise localisation for robot grasping	Outdoor, indoor	Objects, static or low mobility	Use Case 1: DISAC for smart factory shop floors And Use Case 2: VRU protection at a smart intersection
Micro-deformation sensing	Outdoor	Building, bridge, other infrastructure, static with vibration/deformation	
Traffic throughput and safety on road intersections	Outdoors	Pedestrian, vehicles with low/medium mobility	Use Case 2: VRU protection at a smart intersection Merged use case: DISAC-Assisted Parking
Collaborative robots based on digital twinning	Indoors	Objects, robots with low mobility	Use Case 1: DISAC for smart factory shop floors
Body proximity sensor	Indoor, outdoor	Human target, static, low mobility (centimetre level)	
High resolution topographical maps	Outdoor	Static objects/buildings, humans, vehicles with all mobility levels	
Outdoor healthcare sensing and monitoring	Outdoor	Humans with low mobility	
R-CPS in industrial worksites	Indoor	Humans, objects, robots, static or with low mobility	
Safe & economic UAV transport	Outdoor	UAVs, aircrafts	
Emergency vehicle route planning	Outdoors	Vehicles with low/medium/high mobility, environment objects	
Sensing-aided communications	Indoor and outdoor	All types of communication application	
Automated guided vehicles travelling in airports	Large indoor area or mixed indoor/outdoor area.	Humans or vehicles with low/medium mobility	
Vision-aided sensing	Outdoors	Vehicles with low/medium/high mobility and humans	

Some of these use cases require support for small scale motion/micro-movements (human motion, infrastructure vibration, fine tools movements) and a KPI named “Fine Motion accuracy” has been added for this purpose. Another new KPI is Sensing Service Range which refers to a distance in one or more axis from a reference point. The GR also points out the work on channel modelling would need to take into consideration RCS modelling covering a vast number of target types, and some use case specificities requiring micro-Doppler or near-field modelling.

3 Enhancing Selected ISAC Use Cases using the DISAC Framework

3.1 Overview of Key DISAC Use Cases and Composite Scenario

Among the many use cases identified across standardisation bodies and industry fora, the 6G-DISAC consortium has selected a focused set of use cases, originally introduced in [6GDISAC-D21]. The selected DISAC use cases, DISAC for smart factory shop floors and Vulnerable Road User (VRU) protection at smart intersections, as described in the previous deliverable, were chosen based on their strong potential to benefit from distributed sensing capabilities. As mentioned in [6GDISAC-D21], the identified criteria are as follows:

- **DISAC Benefit:** Use cases that stand to gain the most from a distributed architecture. These scenarios demand high-precision localisation, target detection, and identification with exceptional reliability, robustness, and resilience — all of which are core strengths of DISAC, enabled through its advanced signal processing and distributed sensing capabilities.
- **Business Potential:** Use cases that offer strong revenue opportunities not only for network operators but also for a wide range of stakeholders within vertical industries such as smart cities and industrial automation.
- **Demonstration Potential:** Use cases where the consortium has the expertise, existing Proofs of Concept (PoCs), and testbeds necessary to effectively demonstrate and validate the system's performance.

In addition to the primary use cases described in [6GDISAC-D21], the consortium has identified a composite use case that, while not entirely new, emerges as a convergence of the previously defined scenarios, demonstrating the full potential of the DISAC framework. This integrated use case showcases how DISAC can operate synergistically across multiple verticals, combining, for instance, aspects of industrial automation with urban safety features. By leveraging the strengths of both smart factory and smart intersection scenarios, this use case serves as a unified demonstration of DISAC's scalability, adaptability, and semantic-awareness. Its versatility and broad relevance make it an ideal candidate for real-world validation and promotion within WP5 demonstration activities, helping to illustrate the practical impact of DISAC in diverse environments.

3.2 Merged use case: DISAC-Assisted Parking

This newly defined use case merges the strengths of two earlier scenarios — *sensor-augmented AGV navigation in smart factories* and *VRU protection at smart intersections* — into a unified and scalable concept. Specifically, it addresses the challenges and opportunities of mixed indoor-outdoor mobility environments, focusing on scenarios such as smart parking facilities seamlessly connected to public or semi-public spaces. The primary goals are to enhance parking convenience, support parking automation, and significantly increase safety through infrastructure-based sensing, as depicted in Figure 3-1.

In this scenario, a vehicle equipped with an SAE Level 2 driving system begins its journey parked in an indoor parking area. SAE Level 2 refers to a conditionally automated driving mode where the vehicle can control both steering and acceleration/deceleration, but the driver remains responsible for monitoring the environment and must be ready to take over at any time. The driver initiates a maneuver to exit the indoor parking spot and move towards an outdoor parking location, such as a designated drop-off zone or parking bay. This trajectory follows a linear path from the indoor to the outdoor environment and is continuously supported by a sensor-rich infrastructure that provides real-time situational awareness and trajectory recommendations. Using a combination of fixed infrastructure-mounted sensors, including radar, LiDAR, and cameras, as well as advanced elements like reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RISs) to enhance sensing coverage and expand the spatial diversity of the propagated signal, the

Figure 3-1: Assisted and automated parking (use case overview).

infrastructure monitors the environment far beyond the perception range of the vehicle's onboard sensors. It detects potential hazards such as pedestrians, cyclists, or other moving objects, even in occluded or visually complex areas. The extended sensing capabilities provided by the infrastructure enable a safer and more convenient driving and parking experience. Specifically, the infrastructure is in charge of:

- **Localising the vehicle precisely**, even in GNSS-shadowed indoor areas.
- **Identifying and communicating the location of available parking spaces**, streamlines the parking search and also enables prioritisation for emergency vehicles and service vehicles involved in accident response or infrastructure maintenance.
- **Providing detailed information about available space dimensions**, facilitating automated parking maneuvers.
- **Detecting VRUs, such as pedestrians and cyclists, in the vehicle's surroundings**, even in occluded or visually complex areas. It then provides timely warnings to the driver or, if necessary, initiates braking to prevent collisions.

This extended sensing capability enables a cooperative driving experience, where the infrastructure acts as an intelligent assistant, enhancing the driver's awareness and enabling safer, more informed decisions during the maneuver. This concept also opens the door to future extensions, where the vehicle could eventually operate in a higher level of automation, such as SAE Level 4, by either fusing infrastructure sensing data with its own onboard perception or receiving direct motion commands from the infrastructure.

4 Sensing modality analysis

A preliminary analysis of the duplexing constraints was already conducted in D2.1 (see section 4.5 of [6GDISAC-D21]), where it was pointed out that "Frequency Division Duplexing (FDD) and Time Division Duplexing (TDD) duplexing modes, which are implemented in nowadays commercial mobile communication systems, impose limitations on the ability to perform simultaneous sensing and communication effectively".

Building upon that foundation, current work shifts focus toward studying which sensing modalities could be realistically deployed under various practical constraints beyond the ones related to the duplexing techniques. These include standardisation limitations, as well as the inherent challenges of adapting sensing functionalities to existing communication systems. To this end,

further analysis has been carried out on sensing modalities, not only evaluating their compatibility with different duplexing schemes but also assessing requirements such as position knowledge, synchronisation, and reference signal availability.

The final results of such analysis are summarised in Table 4-1, where the following color code applies, to visually describe if and how much critical or challenging in realisation each investigated aspect is for each analysed sensing modality:

- not critical
- manageable
- critical

Table 4-1: Sensing modality analysis.

Sensing modality	Duplexing compatibility	Position(s) knowledge	Synchronisation needs	Reference signal knowledge
Monostatic	Not compatible with standard duplexing hardware <i>solution: full-duplex hardware or sniffer¹ to be added to standard gNB → additional costs</i>	measurements in local frame of reference	perfect self-synchronisation	Early-stage deployment with minimum cost
Bistatic gNB → UE UE → gNB	Compatible with standard duplexing	UE position needs to be known <i>solution: UE can be replaced with positioning reference unit (PRU) → additional costs or estimated using simultaneous localisation and mapping (SLAM) → increased uncertainty</i>	UE needs to be synchronised with gNB <i>solution: LoS path can be used as a reference, provided it exists and it is resolved</i>	TX signal should be known at the receiver <i>solution: pilots can be used or detected data symbols used as pilots</i>
Bistatic UE → UE	Compatible with standard sidelink ²	both UE positions need to be known, in either a local or global coordinate system <i>solution: UE position must be achieved with a separate process</i>	UEs need to be time-synchronised in a local or global time reference <i>solution: LoS path can be used for synchronisation in local time reference, provided it exists and it is resolved</i>	TX signal should be known at the receiver <i>solution: pilots or detected data symbols used as pilots can be used</i>
Bistatic gNB → gNB	Not compatible with standard duplexing <i>solution: full-duplex hardware or sniffer¹ to be added to</i>	gNB positions are known	gNBs need to be synchronised <i>solution: can be achieved with GPS or cables</i>	Transmit signal should be known at the receiver <i>solution: pilots can be used or TX data</i>

¹ A “sniffer” is a receiver placed close to the RU of BS (it could be just another RU reconfigured to working all the time as a receiver only). Of course, its position entails interference issues from the nearby RU transmits signals during ordinary BS operations. Applied to nowadays commercial mobile communication systems, it means an extra CAPEX and OPEX for operators.

² Sidelink communication is direct communication between two UEs without the participation of a BS in the transmission and reception of data traffic [HSB+21] [3GPP38.859] .

Sensing modality	Duplexing compatibility	Position(s) knowledge	Synchronisation needs	Reference signal knowledge
	standard gNB → additional costs			symbols can be sent to RX gNB
Multistatic UE → gNB(s) gNB(s) → UE	Compatible with standard duplexing	gNB positions are known gNBs can be seen as a “large antenna” under phase coherence	gNBs need to be mutually synchronised (time or phase) UE can be time and phase synchronised from the pilots and known gNB locations phase coherence very difficult to attain and requires precise geometry calibration	compatible with typical D-MIMO pilot transmission concepts, at least in up-link In downlink, it is a bit different: either the BSs should use orthogonal pilots (like PRS)
Multistatic UE(s) → UE(s)	Master UE and slave UEs mode could be deployed, in TDD, or Sidelink broadcast	Relative position of slave UE according to master UE could be shared among UEs.	Synchronisation is required with respect to the master UE	Transmit signal should be known at the receiver
Multistatic gNB(s) → gNB(s)	Not compatible with standard duplexing solution: full-duplex hardware or sniffer ¹ to be added to standard gNB → additional costs	gNB positions are known	gNBs need to be synchronised solution: can be achieved with GPS or cables	Transmit signal should be known at the receiver solution: pilots can be used or TX data symbols can be sent to RX gNB

Interference is a fundamental challenge in any sensing system involving multiple transmitters (TXs) where coordination mechanisms are essential, even in monostatic configurations where several TXs operate at the same time (see Figure 4-1). In multistatic sensing systems, however, the interference problem becomes particularly critical due to the simultaneous operation of multiple spatially distributed transmitters and receivers. A key issue is self-interference (SI), where a node’s transmitted signal leaks into its own receiver, potentially obscuring weak echoes from targets. This challenge is further intensified by cross-interference between different transmitter-receiver pairs, leading to multiple overlapping signals within the environment. Such interference can significantly degrade the signal-to-noise ratio, increase the likelihood of false detections, and complicate the overall signal processing workflow.

Regarding bistatic and multistatic sensing modalities, it is important to note that sensing results are not directly available at each individual node. Instead, preliminary data are first processed locally by the Sensing Processing Function (SePF) at each node. Then, these locally processed results are transmitted to a centralised SePF, where data from all nodes are fused to generate a comprehensive sensing outcome. This consolidated result is subsequently provided to the Sensing Management Function (SeMF) for storage and distribution upon request. The protocol and message exchange mechanisms enabling this process are detailed in Deliverable D4.1 [6GDISAC-D41], which complements the architectural description provided in Deliverable D2.2 [6GDISAC-D22].

Results presented in Table 4-1 are the basis of a discussion, which is still ongoing among WP3, WP4 and WP5 at the time current document gets released, to decide which sensing modality should be prioritised. Anyway, the following conclusions can already be stated.

- For monostatic sensing, the BS-centric modality is more likely to be implemented in practice by means of a BS with full-duplex hardware or a sniffer than the UE-centric one.
- For bistatic, and similarly multistatic, sensing,
 - the BS-UE and UE-BS modalities are compatible with the duplexing schemes implemented in nowadays commercial mobile communication systems, but attention should be paid to the UE position knowledge and synchronisation needs;
 - the BS-BS modality could work if a sniffer is introduced, even though interference issues with the TDD duplexing still hold true and have to be taken into account;
 - the UE-UE modality looks challenging due to the unknown locations of the UEs.

Figure 4-1: Interference must be considered in all sensing configurations involving multiple transmitters.

5 KPIs and Metrics for the DISAC Framework

In Deliverable [6GDISAC-D21], a structured and comprehensive overview of the KPIs and metrics relevant to the DISAC framework could be found. The document presented the communication and sensing-related KPIs derived from standardisation bodies and state-of-the-art research, reflecting the dual focus of DISAC. It also explored the influence of semantic communications on these KPIs, emphasising the 6G shift toward goal-oriented metrics and the ever-increasing importance of user intent and information relevance. Furthermore, the concept of KVIs was introduced to complement traditional KPIs by capturing societal objectives such as sustainability, inclusiveness, and trust. A DISAC-specific set of metrics was proposed, organised into communication, sensing, and ISAC trade-off categories. Finally, the trade-offs inherent to ISAC systems at both the radio resource and system levels were discussed, highlighting the need for a balanced approach to optimise technical performances while aligning with broader societal goals.

5.1 Summary of KPI and KVI from SDOs

In [6GDISAC-D21], relevant KPIs and KVIs for the DISAC framework were addressed, based on standards like 3GPP, ETSI, and IEEE, as well as state-of-the-art research. The KPIs are categorised into two main groups: communication-oriented (focusing on communication performance such as data rate, outage probability, latency, reliability and energy efficiency) and sensing-oriented (focusing on sensing capabilities such as sensing accuracy, resolution, detection rate, false alarm, sensing range/coverage, latency, classification accuracy, continuity of sensing and energy efficiency). Additionally, the influence of Semantic Communications on these KPIs

was explored. To align 6G ISAC systems with broader societal objectives, KVIs, covering sustainability, inclusiveness, and trustworthiness, are also introduced in [6GDISAC-D21], offering a more comprehensive approach to system evaluation.

Although the 6G-DISAC project does not explicitly address any KVIs at this stage, the influence of KVIs on technology development, particularly in fostering social acceptance, is well recognised. As indicated in the 6G4Society Survey on 6G Social Acceptance which is currently under development [SOS+25], the project focuses on integrating privacy, personal health and protection from harm, as well as the three sustainability key values (Environmental, Societal, Economic). For our consortium, a key objective is to ensure that the new technology under study and development considers its future social acceptance and exploitability: the aim is to align technological innovations with broader societal, economic, and environmental goals, rather than focusing solely on technical performance. The technology should be guided by performance measurements, identifying and enabling values, for a value-based network design. KVIs have the potential to transform the technology design process from purely being performance-centric, to incorporating considerations of technological and societal values. The project is encountering several challenges in identifying suitable KVIs, particularly in selecting which values to develop indicators for, defining measurable indicators within the project's timeframe, handling qualitative data, validating the process, and applying KVIs to our low Technology Readiness Level (TRL) demonstrators.

The social acceptance of 6G technologies and multiple use cases promising to be enabled, could be balanced by possible societal benefits, as for the positive impact on digital divide. The fact that for some more fragile categories of persons the access to and the use of some applications is more difficult or hindered, is expected to be reduced by the introduction of 6G applications, for several reasons. ISAC (and by extension DISAC) can unlock services in an intuitive way, such as new forms of interfaces, or gesture detection, making applications more user friendly as fed by AI and ISAC, so less effort required by users. The new technologies have the possibility to offer digital applications that are "transparent" to users (e.g., high accuracy localisation for existing mobile applications, autonomous driving, smart cities). The 6G-DISAC project targets to show how the 6G technologies may provide increased (and/or more affordable) connectivity in underserved areas, also leveraging AI, which may lead to more accessible interactions with digital services, as proposed in [6GDISAC-D31] and [6GDISAC-D41].

5.2 KPIs and KVIs in DISAC project

Crucially, both the communication and the sensing objectives may describe diverse scenarios and use cases, that call for different functionalities to be developed and supported. So, the dual objective of ISAC introduces inherent trade-offs in the design, deployment, and operation of such systems. For those purposes, the quantification and evaluation of the performance of ISAC system necessitates the introduction of several KPIs, each associated with a specific system benefit or cost. From the communication perspective in PHY, the underlying KPIs reflect the quality of the physical link for data transmission and align with KPIs of conventional communication systems. The sensing objective under ISAC can be interpreted more broadly. Sensing may refer to (a) the detection of presence, position, or physical attributes of not connected (passive) users or objects, e.g., similar to radar systems, (b) the localisation of connected users (UEs), or (c) the estimation of radio properties of the environments, such as channel estimation and RF mapping.

In the light of this wide variety of functionalities, a plurality of KPIs can be defined. The KPIs have been detailed in the previous Deliverable D21 [6GDISAC-D21, section 4] where a set of communication-oriented KPIs and another set of sensing-oriented KPIs were outlined. The remainder of this section describes the KPIs and metrics used under 6G-DISAC to evaluate the technical methodologies and support the use cases highlighted in this deliverable. Each KPI is

associated with a set of metrics that can be used for its evaluation. To give a harmonised overview of the advancements of the project, the contributions presented in [6GDISAC-D31] and [6GDISAC-D41] are reported in relation to the metrics used.

In the following section, the canonical KPIs are described first, serving as fundamental metrics for evaluating the core functionalities of the project. Subsequently, the composite KPIs are introduced, integrating multiple aspects of performance to provide a more comprehensive assessment. Finally, the relationship between these KPIs and all the contributions made within the project is explored, highlighting how each contribution aligns with and supports the defined KPIs. This structured approach ensures a clear understanding of the project's progress and the effectiveness of its methodologies.

5.2.1 Canonical KPIs

The canonical metric in this context is the Symbol Error Rate or Bit Error Rate (*SER* or *BER*): The probability that a transmitted symbol or bit is incorrectly decoded at the receiver. It quantifies the reliability of a modulation scheme and depends on the SNR, modulation order, and channel conditions.

- **Localisation accuracy:** Quantifies the estimation error of some location parameters (coordinates in a frame of reference, angle or distance with respect to known anchor points, etc.) of a UE on the network. In particular, assuming that the true location of the UE is known and given some estimated parameter(s), the following metrics are defined:
 - *Position Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE):* Corresponds to the root of the squared difference between the true and estimated coordinates of the UE, over various candidate positions.
 - *Position estimation error:* The absolute difference between estimated and true coordinates of the UE, for its current position.
 - *Distance estimation error:* The absolute difference between estimated and true distance of the current location of the UE from a reference point (typically, a known anchor points such as a BS).
 - *Angle estimation error:* The absolute difference between estimated and true angle (Azimuth and/or Elevation) of the current location of the UE from a reference point.
 - *Time Difference of Arrival (TDoA) error:* The difference between the estimated and true time of arrival, used in localisation techniques that rely on measuring the time it takes for beacon signals to travel from the sensed object to the anchor points.
 - *Position Error Bound (PEB):* Represents the theoretical limit on the accuracy of position estimation, indicating the best achievable performance given the available measurements and system conditions.
 - *Cramér-Rao Bound (CRB):* A statistical lower bound on the variance of any unbiased estimator for position, serving as a benchmark for the optimal accuracy that can be achieved in a given localisation system.
- **Target detection capability:** Refers to the identification of the presence of a non-connected user (target) of the system over a monitored radio area.
 - *Probability of detection:* It measures the likelihood of correctly detecting a target when the target is actually present. It is expressed as the number of true detections over the sum of all reported detections (true and false ones).
 - *Detection accuracy:* Expressed as the number of correctly identified instances of target's presence (or absence) over the total number of trials.
 - *F1-score:* Provides a metric that balances erroneous detections and missed detections which is defined as the harmonic mean of Type I and Type II errors.
 - *Detection latency:* This is defined by the number of messages (transmissions of reference signals) that are required for correct detection of a target.

- **Sensing resolution:** In the context of multi-antenna systems, the sensing resolution directly corresponds to the shape of the constructed lobe of the antenna array. In particular, the following metrics are used to quantify the properties of the lobe:
 - *Main Lobe Width (MLW):* Measures the angular width of the main lobe of the beam pattern constructed by the antenna. Narrower lobes offer high-grained resolution.
 - *Peak Sidelobe Level (PSL):* Measures the maximum gain of any of the side lobes of the antenna pattern in relation to the gain of the main lobe. High PSLs indicate less directional beams that have diverse effects on the accurate localisation of the sensing target.
- **Imaging fidelity:** In radio imaging scenarios, where the 2D or 3D surfaces (boundaries) of the objects placed within the wireless environment are to be retrieved, based on radio signals, typical localisation and detection metrics do not convey the complete information. Instead, metrics from the domain of image processing are typically borrowed. In practice, the surveyed area is discretised into a grid of “pixels”, and the systems outputs either a binary value for each one (indicating the presence or not of part of an object in the corresponding grid cells) or a continuous value corresponding to its material properties (e.g., permittivity) for that cell. The considered metrics are therefore:
 - *Pixel-wise Mean Square Error (MSE):* It is expressed as the average MSE between the true value of a property of an object and its estimated value on each pixel of the surveyed area.
 - *Binary Cross Entropy (BCE):* A metric for binary classification tasks that evaluates how close the estimated binary values indicating the presence of an object at a certain pixel are to the true values (i.e., whether part of the object actually appears in that pixel). The values are treated as probabilities and the metric penalises confident wrong predictions more heavily and encourages confident correct ones. BCE is typically used as a surrogate for detection accuracy in learning-based approaches due to its convenient mathematical properties.
- **Semantic accuracy:** When semantic and goal-oriented communications are employed as part of the control plane to exchange relevant features of the observed signals instead of transmitting the complete data, the evaluation of the system requires novel metrics that capture the successful decoding of the meaning of the data. One key metric used in this context is classification accuracy, which applies when transmitted signals are assigned to one of several predefined categories, each representing distinct environmental meanings (e.g., presence or absence of a blocker, or type of sensed object). Classification accuracy is then defined as the ratio of correctly identified class instances to the total number of instances in a given dataset.

5.2.2 Composite KPIs

The *composite* KPIs, *i.e.*, system performances, express potential costs associated with achieving desired primary KPI levels and are used to quantify efficiency and scalability. They are used to quantify the requirements and resources for achieving the system objectives. The metrics for each of the following composite KPIs are constructed by dividing the metric value corresponding to one of the primary KPIs with a constrain/requirement value (e.g., the communication power efficiency can be computed as the achieved SER/BER over the transmission power). According to this definition, the following composite KPIs are addressed in 6G-DISAC:

- **Communication power efficiency:** Estimated by evaluating any communication metric over the transmission power.
- **Sensing power efficiency:** It is defined similarly, by evaluating any localisation, detection, or sensing metric over the required transmission power.
- **Spectral efficiency:** Measures the spectral resources allocated to the system to achieve a target KPI. Different from the spectral efficiency in terms of communication

that relates to the channel capacity, this KPI is used in a more general purpose for any ISAC KPI.

- **Spatial efficiency:** It quantifies the number of antenna elements or devices required for achieving a target KPI. This conveys a notion of scalability in terms of required infrastructure.
- **Computational complexity:** It is expressed as the number of computational units required to achieve any target KPI. When deep learning computational models are employed, the units of computation are defined as the number of neural network weights.
- **Semantic Spectral Efficiency (SSE):** Refers to the rate at which semantic information can be successfully transmitted over a unit of bandwidth and is measured in semantic units per second per Hz [YQZ+22].

5.2.3 KPIs and metrics in different contributions

The technical contributions of [6GDISAC-D31] and [6GDISAC-D41] are categorised according to the metrics and KPIs addressed in Table 5-1. Contributions starting with #A-, #B-, and #C- correspond to contributions from [6GDISAC-D31], while contributions numbered as #P- and #O- are contributions from [6GDISAC-D41].

It is worth noting that, through the analysis of the Table 5-1 listing all contributions, it is clear that communication performance has not been neglected in favour of sensing. On the contrary, particular attention has been given to ensuring that communication performance is preserved and optimized alongside sensing functionalities. Several contributions presented in Deliverable D3.1 such as #A-4 #C-2, #B-8 etc. address the balance of resource allocation between communication and sensing, proposing strategies to manage potential trade-offs and optimize joint performance. This balanced approach highlights the commitment to maintaining robust communication capabilities while enabling efficient and effective sensing within the same system framework. Moreover, this table summarizes all the contributions presented in Deliverables D31 [6GDISAC-D31] and D4.1 [6GDISAC-D41], demonstrating how the project has fulfilled the objectives we set, including managing resource allocation between sensing and communication, as well as addressing trade-offs between processing requirements, power consumption, and sensing accuracy. By leveraging the advantages of distributed sensing, as detailed in D4.1, the approach distributes power consumption across sensing nodes instead of concentrating data processing in a single centralized node. This distributed architecture not only reduces the burden on individual nodes but also enhances overall system efficiency and scalability.

Table 5-1: Considered KPIs and metrics by the technical contributions of D3.1 and D4.1.

KPI	Metric	Contribution number (D3.1/D4.1)
Communication performance	SNR	#C-3
	SINR	#O-1
	Capacity/Rate	#A-4, #C-2, #O-1, #O-7, #O-9
	SER	#A-5
User/target localisation accuracy	Position RMSE	#A-2, #B-2, #B-5, #B-6, #B-7, #B-12
	Position estimation error	#B-9, #B-10, #B-11, #O-3, #O-6
	Angle estimation error	#B-7, #C-2, #O-4
	Distance estimation error	#B-7, #B-8, #C-2, #O-4
	TDoA error	#B-2
	PEB	#A-2, #A-3, #B-1, #B-3, #B-4
Target detection capability	CRB	#A-5, #B-2, #C-2
	Probability of detection	#A-4, #B-11, #B-12, #B-13
	Detection accuracy	#C-1
	F1-score	#A-1, #C-1
Sensing resolution	Detection latency	#O-2, #O-5
	MLW	#O-7

	PSL	#O-7
Imaging fidelity	Pixel-wise MSE	#B-14, #B-15
	BCE	#B-14
Semantic accuracy	Classification accuracy	#B-14, #P-7, #O-8
Communication power efficiency	SNR/Data rate over transmission power	#B-5, #C-2, #P-3
Sensing power efficiency	Detection probability over transmission power	#A-5, #B-12, #B-13, #O-4
	Detection error over transmission power	#B-2, #C-2
	PEB over transmission power	#B-7, #C-3, #P-3
	Classification accuracy over transmission power	#A-1, #O8
Spectral efficiency	Detection probability over bandwidth	#O-5
	PEB over bandwidth	#B-4
Spatial efficiency	Detection probability over Nb. of sensors	#A-2, B-9, #B-10, #O-2
	Classification accuracy over Nb. of antenna elements	#B-14, #O-8
	Data rate over Nb. of MIMO beamformers	#O-9
Computational complexity	Classification accuracy over Nb. of neural network parameters	#B-14, #O-8
	Data rate over Nb. of neural network parameters	#P-8, #O-9
Semantic efficiency	SSE	#A-1, #P-7

With the exception of spatial efficiency, which quantifies the required number of nodes needed to achieve the system goals, the aforementioned KPIs can be applied to either centralised or distributed ISAC systems. However, distributed architectures are posed to bring notable performance improvements with minimal increase in operation costs [MMP+25], [HSL+22], as they consume less energy by leveraging already deployed, low-power equipment for sensing, unlike centralised systems that require dedicated, high-power hardware to achieve similar performance. As a result, an elaboration is required on how distributed systems can offer KPI improvements. The particular details on candidate approaches are described in the technical contributions of WP3 and WP4 of this project in terms of sensing & communication algorithms, waveform and system design, messaging exchange protocols, and orchestration schemes. Nevertheless, a high-level discussion is included in this section to address specifically the metrics, KPIs, and architectural components of 6G-DISAC.

Channel estimation accuracy is vital for ISAC systems, which need to gather information about the propagation medium while communicating. This task is especially difficult in distributed networks with multiple links that have varying fading conditions, and where multiple nodes require precise synchronisation and resource allocation. To evaluate channel sensing quality, two metrics can be used: MSE and CRB. The introduction of multiple nodes acting as base stations (BSs) enhances BS-user association policies, similar to those in cellular networks. By addressing propagation and mobility conditions, as well as Quality of Service (QoS) requirements, each user equipment (UE) can be matched with the most favourable node to establish a communication link, thereby improving communication performance in multi-user systems. Even in single-user scenarios, distributed MIMO (D-MIMO) systems offer advantages over centralised variants due to higher spatial diversity derived from distributed antenna elements, which can be leveraged to design spatial multiplexing schemes and enhance data rates.

In terms of KPIs related to sensing performance, the distribution of nodes offers even more pronounced comparative advantages. The main performance benefits are derived from the gains of multi-static sensing over simpler monostatic and bistatic systems. In particular, distributed sensing TXs (STxs)/sensing RXs (SRxs) provide sufficient signal diversity to obtain accurate position estimations for the environmental objects. The selection of the most useful nodes to participate in the sensing process can further reduce the errors in terms of distance and angle estimations. Additionally, the redundancy of sensing signals improves the probability of detection of passive objects and blockers. Finally, multi-static systems provide diverse fields-of-view of the sensed objects that are instrumental in performing high-fidelity imaging of the object surfaces.

This sub-selection of resources has simultaneously a positive impact on KPIs related to efficiency. Since only devices that result in better performance are selected, the system may not waste resource units in activating nodes with limited effect on a particular functionality. In terms of power efficiency, for example, the nearest BS/STx/SRx may be activated, resulting to lower transmission power requirements for localisation and communication. From the perspective of computational efficiency, DISAC architectures, as described in Deliverable D2.2 [6GDISAC-D22], can take advantage of distributed Local Sensing Processing Function (LSePFs) units co-located with particular devices on the network. As a result, favourable trade-offs between local computation and data exchange can be achieved by allocating parts of the computation on local devices, where the data become available, while transmitting intermediate processed results (e.g., data representations, semantic symbols, or neural network parameters) over control channels.

Despite the foreseen benefits of distributed systems on ISAC-related KPIs, the operation of such networks comes with important challenges. Control and feedback links need to be established among the distributed devices as well as between devices and the Central Sensing Processing Function (CSepF) as well as the SeMF, as defined in [6GDISAC-D22]. The orchestration and allocation of resources on such systems may increase the design complexity and operational costs. To this end, the work carried out in WP4 of this Project [6GDISAC-D41] addresses the above challenges in developing messaging exchange protocols and orchestration schemes to orchestrate DISAC networks toward achieving the expected KPI values.

5.3 Semantic Communication for Enhanced Sensing: Key Outcomes

In the context of semantic-empowered communication, an effective data exchange is not related to transmitting more data, faster, while preserving the signal integrity, as in traditional communication framework. Instead, it is about transmitting the right data, in the right context, at the right time, and with the right purpose. Goal-driven semantic communication is recognised to be one of the most predominant enablers for 6G networks, aspiring to become networks that understand and serve either human or machine goals.

Then, from a semantic communication perspective, semantic KPIs emphasise goal completion, task success, adaptability, and contextual understanding. These metrics are designed not only to quantify transmitted data but also to assess system-level intelligence, energy efficiency, and responsiveness in real-world applications. They reflect how wireless networks are capable of discerning which data matters most, why it matters, and when and how to act upon it, and aim to measure how effectively a system understands and responds to specific needs. In the DISAC context, this includes processing and transmitting only essential data from distributed sensors, using semantic reasoning and fusion centres to issue intelligent, goal-driven instructions. In [6GDISAC-D21], the critical metrics for 6G semantic communications were discussed. Emphasis was placed on how semantic communication significantly strengthens the DISAC framework, enabling smarter, goal-oriented decision-making across distributed systems.

In [HHC+25], a novel semantic-aware waveform design for AI-native 6G networks is proposed, as further detailed in [6GDISAC-D31] and [6GDISAC-D41]. The contribution leverages the **F1**

score, a machine learning evaluation metric that assesses the predictive skill of a model by elaborating on its class-wise performance rather than an overall performance as done by accuracy. The F1 score is based on the *Confusion Matrix*, representing the predictive performance of a model on a dataset, and mainly relying on the counts of instances correctly and incorrectly classified (Figure 5-1-a). F1 score combines two competing metrics, precision and recall scores of a model, using their harmonic mean, such that maximising the F1 score implies simultaneously maximising both precision and recall (Figure 5-1-b). Specifically for our case, the F1 score quantifies the balance between precision and recall when identifying correct triplets (concept-relationship-concept) in the proposed knowledge graphs. The precision is the proportion of correctly identified triplets in the inferred knowledge graph, out of all identified triplets, and recall is the proportion of correctly identified triplets in the inferred knowledge graph, out of all triplets present in the source knowledge graph.

Figure 5-1: a) Structure of a Confusion Matrix; b) Formulas for Precision and Recall metrics.

Furthermore, the performance of the proposed contribution is measured also through the **semantic spectral efficiency**, defined not merely in bits per second per Hz, but in correctly interpreted semantic symbols per Hz per second at the receiver [YQZ+22]. This implies a shift in design philosophy: from bit-accuracy to controlled degradation and robustness, where only semantically significant distortions matter.

5.4 System performance evaluation through KVIs

To ensure that 6G ISAC systems align with broader societal goals, it is important to understand and evaluate their performance through KVIs. The 6G-DISAC framework considers the following KVIs:

- Sustainability: environmental, social and economic;
- Inclusiveness: geographical, socioeconomic, and accessible for all;
- Trustworthiness: evaluated in terms of robustness, security and privacy.

5.4.1 Sustainability

a) **Environmental sustainability**: To enhance environmental sustainability, the 6G-DISAC framework adopts a range of strategies aimed at improving energy efficiency and minimising waste. These include optimising radio resource allocation to reduce unnecessary energy consumption and employing energy-efficient hardware, such as Reconfigurable Intelligent

Surfaces (RISs). Adaptive algorithms are utilised to further decrease power usage by dynamically adjusting system operations based on real-time requirements. The integration of positioning and sensing with communication infrastructure reduces the need for additional deployments, while semantic reasoning ensures that only essential data is processed and transmitted. Energy efficiency is further improved through distributed ISAC functionality, which enables more effective electromagnetic field (EMF) control, and by shortening the distances between user equipment (UEs) and base stations (BSs), thereby lowering transmission power. The use of RISs also minimises reliance on conventional, energy-intensive infrastructure like base stations and relays. Additionally, semantic communication techniques and goal-oriented network management contribute to optimised energy use, supported by physical layer (PHY) innovations such as semantic-aware waveform design.

- b) Social sustainability:** The 6G-DISAC framework supports social sustainability by fostering a more connected society through equitable access to advanced communication and sensing services. It places a strong emphasis on managing electromagnetic field (EMF) exposure to protect public health, ensuring that technological advancements do not compromise safety. Additionally, the framework aims to enhance traffic safety and promote inclusive, safe mobility services for all users. By optimising the integration of sensing and communication infrastructure, 6G-DISAC also contributes to improving urban environmental health, supporting healthier and more sustainable living environments in increasingly connected cities.
- c) Economic sustainability:** The 6G-DISAC framework promotes economic sustainability by facilitating cross-fertilisation between traditional industries and emerging technologies, such as advanced materials, sensors, and artificial intelligence. This integration creates new business opportunities for a wide range of stakeholders, fostering innovation and supporting long-term economic growth. Additionally, the framework emphasises the maximisation of resource reuse—including network equipment, radio resources, and spectrum—to ensure more sustainable and cost-effective economic operations within the evolving 6G ecosystem.

5.4.2 Inclusiveness

The 6G-DISAC framework prioritises inclusiveness by ensuring that advanced 6G services are accessible to all, regardless of geographical location or socioeconomic background. It promotes universal accessibility with the goal of leaving no user behind in the digital transformation. To support this, the framework incorporates dynamic spectrum sharing and multi-RIS-enabled smart environments, which enable more efficient spectrum utilisation. These innovations also facilitate the generation of 3D environmental mapping, allowing for shared use among different spectrum owners and further promoting equitable access to advanced communication and sensing capabilities.

5.4.3 Trustworthiness

Trustworthiness within the 6G-DISAC framework is assessed through key dimensions of robustness, security, and privacy. To enhance these aspects, the framework integrates cooperative communication strategies that improve network resilience, reliability, and the scalability of both sensing and communication functions. It carefully balances redundancy, which supports robustness, with resource efficiency to avoid unnecessary overhead. Additionally, AI-based resource sharing techniques are applied to ensure that network operations remain secure, intelligent, and reliable, addressing the evolving demands of modern communication systems.

5.4.4 Distributed and Semantic-Aided Architecture

The 6G-DISAC framework introduces a sustainable-by-design approach with the introduction of a distributed and semantic-aided architecture design helping in data processing and transmission reduction. Furthermore, the use of sensing and an intelligent parsimonious resource management, leads to energy efficiency. The 6G-DISAC distributed architecture is envisioned to facilitate the sharing of appropriate information from sensing modules to enable enhanced communications, as well as an intelligent sharing and cooperation among different network elements. Innovative RAN solutions are proposed to support multi-band operation, integrated sensing and communication techniques, and the orchestration of local and centralised processing sharing, considering the characteristics of the various network nodes and the transmission network. Techniques for efficiently utilising/sharing the network's available sensory devices, and consequently, the spectrum they operate on, are designed under constraints on the task's overall energy consumption and EMF exposure. Dynamic spectrum sharing schemes are studied for leveraging multi-RIS-enabled smart wireless environments to extract 3D environmental mapping that can be commonly used by different spectrum owners.

To summarise, 6G-DISAC framework promotes a more balanced distribution of energy and resource usage between the network and end-user devices, leveraging their interdependency to optimise overall system efficiency. New signal processing methods for target detection, estimation, and tracking is devised in the DISAC context, focusing on distributed measurements and inter-device cooperation. The potential of cooperative communication strategies involves the study of novel cooperative techniques that enable multiple transmitters and receivers to share and manage resources and collaborate to optimise communication and sensing performance. These techniques can improve network resilience, reliability, and scalability, adapting to the ever-evolving demands of end-users and IoT applications, without compromising the user device efficiency.

6 Conclusion and Outlook

In this Deliverable 2.3, the objectives outlined in the project proposal have been successfully achieved: scenarios involving the sensing of multiple targets using distributed networks of transmitters and receivers were identified and defined; use cases were developed to leverage the rich information obtained through collaborative sensing, addressing the needs of diverse applications, including those where sensing directly enhances communication performance (i.e., sensing-aided communication).

A detailed analysis of distributed sensing approaches was conducted, demonstrating how aggregating information from multiple nodes improves the field of view, enhances positioning accuracy and speeds estimation, and enables advanced target detection and analysis. Additionally, relevant sensing-aided communication use cases were identified and examined in conjunction with the physical-layer enablers developed in WP3.

Across Deliverables D2.1 and D2.3, a comprehensive set of metrics and KPIs was established for evaluating the defined scenarios and use cases, extending beyond traditional single-node performance indicators. Particular attention was given to critical factors such as sensing data volume, power consumption, and processing costs, as well as key trade-offs between resource allocation for sensing versus communication, and among processing requirements, energy efficiency, and sensing accuracy.

This work provides a solid foundation for the development and evaluation of Distributed and Intelligent ISAC, and sets the stage for advancing 6G sensing and communication systems in subsequent project phases.

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